

Benzoyl derivative of chalkone ; The benzoyl derivative of chalkone was prepared by heating a mixture of chalkone, benzoyl chloride and few drops of pyridine on water bath for five hours. The compounds are listed in Table 2.

2'-Hydroxy-4'-n-Butoxychalkone- α - β -Dibromide : 2'-Hydroxy-4'-n-butoxychalkone (0.5 g) in chloroform (25 ml) was treated with bromine in chloroform (0.4 ml ; 50%). The reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature (25-30°C). Chloroform was removed and the residue was washed with sodium thiosulphate solution (5%) and crystallised from light petroleum ether. The compounds are listed in Table III.

Debromination of α - β Dibromochalkone : A mixture of the above dibromide (0.2 g) and potassium iodide (0.2 g) in dry acetone (25 ml) was refluxed on waterbath at 53°-70° for 2-3 hr. The solid separated after removal of acetone and pouring the contents in water was washed with sodium thiosulphate solution (5%) and crystallised from ethanol. The product was identified as the original chalkone by direct comparison.

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Synthesis and Antiinflammatory Activity of some 6-[2-Amino-(and substituted amino)-4-thiazolyl] benzothiazoles.

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IN an earlier paper¹, we described the synthesis and antiinflammatory properties of a series of 2-(2-amino-4-thiazolyl) benzothiazoles. These compounds were relatively non-toxic and exhibited significant antiinflammatory activity which in some cases approached that of phenylbutazone. In this communication

we report the synthesis of a series of 6-[2-amino-(or substituted amino)-4-thiazolyl] benzothiazoles (I) with a view to testing their antiinflammatory activity.

R=H, CH₃, CF₃ or C₆H₅
R'=H or Aryl

2-Methyl-6- benzothiazolyl methyl ketone (II) was prepared from *p*-aminoacetophenone which was thiocyanated and then converted to 4-amino-3-mercaptoacetophenone³. The latter was condensed with acetic anhydride in acetic acid to get the ketone (II). Bromination of the ketone (II) in acetic acid (yield 39%)² was improved by carrying out the reaction in chloroform (yield 59%). 6-Benzothiazolyl bromomethyl ketone and its 2-phenyl and 2-trifluoromethyl analogues were prepared according to the method of Burger and Sawhney⁴. Treatment of these bromomethyl ketones with the appropriate thioureas gave the corresponding compounds in the series I^{1,4}.

Preliminary pharmacological screening of some of the selected compounds in the series has been shown that the compounds possess a good level of antiinflammatory activity, though in general they are less active than 2-(2-amino-4-thiazolyl)-benzothiazoles. The highest activity was observed in compound I, R=R'=H, which showed the inhibition of 45% as compared to 53% shown by phenylbutazone in carageenin rat foot edema test⁵ at a dose level of 100 mg/kg.

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TABLE 1—6-[2-AMINO (AND SUBSTITUTED AMINO)-4-THIAZOLYL] BENZOTHAZOLES(II)

Sr. No.	R	R'	Cryst. from	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analytical Data			
							Found		Required	
							S	N	S	N
1.	H	H	A	166-8	66	C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₃ S ₂	27.10	17.78	27.48	18.02
2.	H	Phenyl	A	176	51	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	20.42	13.20	20.71	13.59
3.	H	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	A	217	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ S ₂	18.38	12.22	18.63	12.23
4.	H	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	A	168	57	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ S ₂	18.29	12.02	18.63	12.23
5.	H	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	A	195	54	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	19.51	12.75	19.81	13.00
6.	H	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	A	140	56	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	19.60	13.47	19.81	13.00
7.	H	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	A	172	61	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS ₂	19.00	12.28	18.88	12.39
8.	H	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	A	250 ^d	55	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	18.30	15.45	18.08	15.82
9.	CH ₃	H	C	226	65	C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	25.69	17.06	25.91	17.00
10.	CH ₃	Phenyl	D	181	55	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ S ₂	19.38	12.72	19.81	13.00
11.	CF ₃	H	C	162	53	C ₁₁ H ₆ F ₃ N ₃ S ₂	*	13.64	—	13.95
12.	CF ₃	Phenyl	C	171	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ F ₃ N ₃ S ₂	**	11.55	—	11.14
13.	CF ₃	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	B	155	53	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ F ₃ N ₃ OS ₂	—	9.98	—	10.32
14.	CF ₃	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	B	163	58	C ₁₇ H ₉ ClF ₃ N ₃ S ₂	—	9.92	—	10.21
15.	C ₆ H ₅	H	B	230	53	C ₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ S ₂	20.36	13.34	20.71	13.59
16.	C ₆ H ₅	Phenyl	C	212-3	50	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂	17.01	10.99	16.62	10.91

* Found : C, 43.52 ; H, 1.68. Required C, 43.85 ; H, 1.99.

** Found : C, 53.94 ; H, 2.65. Required C, 54.11 ; H, 2.65.

A=Alcohol ; B=Alcohol/water ; C=Benzen ; D=Benzene/pet.ether (60°-80°);
E=Xylene · F=Acetic acid.

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Studies on the Infra-red Spectra of Synthetic Humic Acids.

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SEVERAL workers¹⁻⁵ have described the use of infra-red spectroscopy to obtain information about the various atomic groupings and functional groups in soil humic substances and synthesised humus like substances. Flaig⁶ has, however observed that i-r spectra of natural humic acids, synthetic humic acids formed by oxidation of polyphenols and lignin fractions isolated from rotted straw are relatively uncharacteristic, but Ziechmann⁷ shows that well defined absorption occurs at 7-9 μ and at about 10 μ for various peats and synthetic humic acid preparations. A comparative study of the spectra of humic acid from peat, lignite and oxidised hydroquinone with those of various chars and

coals has been made by Eloffson⁸. The present communication deals with comparative studies of the i-r spectra of the synthetic humic substances prepared from different monomers with a view to compare their structural pattern.

Experimental

The methods of preparing the synthetic humic substances have been described in detail earlier⁹. The i. r. spectra in KBr disc (1 mg sample and 300 mg KBr) were recorded on Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer over the region 2.5 μ to 14 μ . The following electro-dialysed samples have been studied :

(i) Hydroquinone humic acid, (ii) Hydroquinone glycine polymer, (iii) catechol humic acid (by O₂), (iv) glucose humic acid, (v) glucose humatmelanic acid, (vi) glucose humic acid (40 hours) and (vii) the nonhydrolysable residues from acid hydrolysis of (a) hydroquinone humic acid, (b) catechol humic acid (c) catechol humic acid (by O₂) and (d) hydroquinone glycine polymer respectively.

Results and Discussion

The infra-red spectra of the different humic acid preparations bear a striking resemblance to one another suggesting that in spite of monomer differences, the polymer formed are closely related structurally. The spectra are, however too diffuse to reveal any significant structural detail. From the data obtained by us the following absorption bands are to be noted particularly in the region 3.45 μ , 5.8 to 5.9 μ , 6.25 to 6.3 μ , 6.6 to 6.7 μ , 7.15 to 7.4 μ , 8.0 to 8.3 μ and 9.8 μ . The relative intensities and sharpness of the contours of the bands are described in Table 1.